

INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE ECONOMISTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219197>

Abstract. *In the article, the purpose, content and result of the stages of the process of forming the readiness of future economists for professional activity were defined in the content and structure of competencies developed at the levels of integration corresponding to the types of activities.*

Keywords: *integration, integrative approach, content of education, professional activity, educational activity, quasiprofessional activity, educational-professional activity, competence.*

An integrative approach is an important factor in improving the process of preparing future economists for professional activity.

The methodological level of the study of integration in education is represented at this stage by its regularities, which are considered as a measure of the difference between the empirical and theoretical development of integration. For example, N.K. Chapaev suggests the following “regularities of the effective construction of integrated learning: a) the conditionality of the tasks and content of integrated learning with the needs of society; b) the effectiveness of integrated learning is ensured by the fulfillment of the intended tasks, its scientific nature and connection with the surrounding life; c) the natural dependence of tasks on the real educational opportunities of students” [4].

L.N. Yastrebova defines the integrative approach as a complex “three-level structure, which includes: a) competence approach (macro approach); b) communicative-cognitive approach (mesopod); c) system approach (micro approach)” [5].

Any form of integrative process in pedagogy has at least two stable characteristics: essential and formal-logical. The essential characteristic of the forms reflects the nature of the integrated objects. On this basis, Yu.S. Tyunnikov [3] identified subject-figurative, conceptual, ideological, activity and conceptual forms. The formal-logical characteristic of the form of integration fixes the degree of density and stability of connections between objects that have entered into integration. Within the framework of the article, we highlight the activity forms.

Consequently, the implementation of an integrative approach to the preparation of future economists for professional activity is not only the development of the content of integrative knowledge, it requires the development of methods for organizing the activities of teachers and students in the study of this material.

In this regard, special attention should be paid to the three basic forms of activity and intermediate between them, which were identified by A.A. Verbitsky [1]. Studying the research of A.A. Verbitsky, we define three main types of activity:

- educational activities (lectures, seminars, independent work, etc.);
- quasiprofessional activities (business games, analysis of specific situations, laboratory work, etc.);
- educational - professional activities (design, industrial practice, preparation of final qualifying works, etc.).

The formation of integration in accordance with the types of activities (educational, quasiprofessional, educational-professional) is characterized by the following three levels: intra-disciplinary integration, interdisciplinary integration, integrity. Integration levels are defined as the internal basis of an integrative approach to preparing students for professional activity.

Intra-disciplinary integration of science is aimed at establishing meaningful, structural and technological links between the branches of science; this makes it possible to identify system-forming links, as well as links between theory and practice.

Interdisciplinary integration is carried out on the basis of integration ideas and system-forming concepts: education, its goals, quality of education, functions and prospects of education, human development, formation of professional content, educational content, methods of cognition, modern educational technologies, in particular technologies of active learning, pedagogical creativity.

Integrity is integration at the level of fundamental ideas, principles, methods of various sciences, providing holistic consciousness, professionalism, understanding of the essence of creative activity and methodological preparation for its implementation.

Integration levels are defined as the internal basis of an integrative approach to the professional training of students. We have conditionally identified three stages of the formation of professional training (subject preparatory stage, professionally oriented stage, general professional stage) by levels of integration (intra-disciplinary integration, interdisciplinary integration, integrity) (table 1).

Table 1

<i>Degree of integration</i>	<i>Stages of the professional training process</i>
Intra-disciplinary integration	Subject preparation
Interdisciplinary integration	Professional orientation
Integrity	General professional

Based on the integrative approach, the purpose, content and the result (levels of training: low, medium, high) of the stages (subject training, professional orientation, general professional) of the formation of professional mathematical training of future economists were determined in the content and structure of competencies formed at the levels of integration, corresponding to the types of activities (table 2).

Table 2.

Pedagogical essence of the system of formation of training of future economists for professional activity

Stages of the professional training process	→ Goal	→ Process	→ Result ↓ (Training levels)	→ Competence
↓ Subject preparation	Understand the importance of subject training for the professional activity of a future economist	Educational activities	A lower level of professional training is being formed	Base competence

↓ Professional orientation	Theoretical and methodological readiness for competitive professional activity	Quasiprofessional activities	The average level of professional training is being formed	Base-professional competence
↓ General professional	Formation of a professional worldview	Educational - professional activities	A high level of professional training is being formed	Professional competence

At each stage, the development of preparatory components in accordance with hierarchical subordination is highlighted as a priority goal, and at each stage the specifics of the effectiveness of activities are taken into account.

The level of formation (low, medium, high) of professional training of future economists was assessed in accordance with cognitive, activity and personal professional criteria that allow us to have a complete picture of the quantitative and qualitative state of the preparatory components presented above.

The cognitive criterion is based on the following quantitative and qualitative indicators of the effectiveness of the received educational process in pedagogy and psychology: filling with knowledge (comparing the student with his initial knowledge), knowledge and practical - the relevance of knowledge in solving issues of economic content, the application of knowledge in new economic processes, the effective use of knowledge in practice. The real amount of knowledge, the use of knowledge in new situations, the effectiveness of knowledge in practice.

The activity criterion allows us to assess the level of formation of cognitive and practical skills (volume; assimilation of the basic theoretical foundations of the skill; completeness of skills; integrativity; flexibility, etc.).

The personal-professional criterion makes it possible to evaluate the axiological description of the learning process: the motives of learning, the personality-specific, professional significance of the acquired knowledge, satisfaction with the educational process, the dynamics of intellectual and physical development, readiness for independent learning.

Based on the integrative approach, we determine the degree of formation of professional training as an effective indicator of the professional competence of a future economist.

According to E.F. Zeer, competencies are the integrative integrity of knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure professional activity, it is the ability of a person to put his competence into practice. The realization of competencies occurs in the process of performing various types of activities to solve theoretical and practical problems, the structure of competencies, in addition to activity (procedural) knowledge, skills and abilities, also includes motivational and emotional-volitional spheres. An important component of competencies is experience – the integration into a single whole of individual actions, methods and techniques of solving problems learned by a person [2]

Therefore, an integrative approach in the framework of professional training of future economists is a set of forms and methods that characterize the process and result of the formation of this competence, accompanied by an increase in the systematic knowledge, the complexity of the student's skills, expressed in theoretical and practical preparedness and contributing to the comprehensive development of personality.

In general, in the process of forming the professional competence of future economists, an integrative approach should be considered as a means of improving the quality of professional training.

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